

Circular Cities & Regions Initiative

Knowledge Hub

Mentoring guide/D3.4

WP 3, T 3.3

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Technical references

Project Acronym	CCRI Knowledge Hub
Project Title	Knowledge hub to leverage existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of Circular economy in Cities and Regions In Europe
Project Coordinator	Kveloce (KVC) ccriknowledgehub@kveloce.com
Project Duration	January 2024 – December 2026 (36 months)
Deliverable No.	D3.4
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 3 – Preparation of customised support services, capacity building and first delivery of services
Task	T3.3 – Identification, recruitment and management of mentors
Lead beneficiary	1 (KVC)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	All
Due date of deliverable	30 September 2024
Actual submission date	26 September 2024

- *PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
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1.1	18/08/2024	UVEG	Carlos Serra (content development)

1.2	27/08/2024	VTT	Satu Paiho (suggetions to section 3.5 and some comments)
2	03/09/2024	KVC	Mireia Ferri (summary and conclusions)
2.1	04/09/2024	CETEC	Enya López (dimension about technology)
3	13/09/2024	VTT, CETEC, INV, EBN, KVC	Example in the dimension description
3.1	16/09/2024	INV	Guillem Figueras (Deliverable revision)
4	26/11/2024	KVC	Mireia Ferri (change of the acronym)
4	20/10/2025	KVC	Updates after the review meeting

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Executive summary

CCRI Knowledge hub connects cities and regions with a pool of experts who provide mentorship services tailored to different stages of the circular economy transition and specific user demands. This mentorship can include strategic advice, technical support, and guidance on policy and regulatory frameworks. In this framework, this deliverable is addressed to experts selected as mentors in charge of providing mentoring services in the framework of the CCRI Knowledge hub project.

Chapter 1 gives an overview of the CCRI Knowledge hub project, and deliverables' aims, scope and audience. Then, the **Chapter 2** described the mentoring one-to-one relationship between mentors and mentees, listing the mentors and mentees roles, responsibilities and rewards related to the Mentoring programme. The **Chapter 3** described the mentoring approach around the four CCRI Knowledge hub dimensions: (i) public engagement, (ii) innovation and technology, (iii) business models and financial support, and (iv) impact evaluation. After, the **Chapter 4** details the process of the mentoring programme, from the mentor selection to the final report delivery. Finally, **Chapter 5** gives some conclusions relevant for the CCRI Knowledge hub Mentoring programme. The deliverable has also **three annexes**, the first one is the template to be used by mentors to draft and deliver the final version of the individual/personalised plan; the second annex provides a template of the contracts to be signed by mentors; and the third annex includes the satisfaction questionnaires to be completed by mentors and mentees once the mentoring programme is finished.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project overview

CCRI Knowledge hub aims to increase the impact of the existing Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) by enlarging the network of involved stakeholders, bringing together the knowledge and critical mass already developed around Circular Economy (CE) implementation and building upon the CE stakeholder platform. The goal is to promote and make the CE concept a reality in EU cities and regions, particularly those in the early stage of CE transition. To reach its objective, CCRI Knowledge hub acts as a “Knowledge hub”, leveraging existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of CE in EU cities and regions. CCRI Knowledge hub’s formula is based on three principles (Figure 1): (a) easy access to systematised workable knowledge; (b) tailored mentoring according to users’ needs and (c) effective awareness-raising to make the CE more desirable, that build upon four main dimensions:

- (i) Public engagement;
- (ii) Innovation and technology;
- (iii) Business models and financial support; and
- (iv) Impact evaluation.

CCRI Knowledge hub gathers a multidisciplinary expert consortium of 11 partners from 6 EU countries (research and technological centres, universities, research organisations, international networks and associations, regional authorities as well as specialised companies and SMEs) that bring in complementary skills and competences to achieve the project’s objectives.

Figure 1: CCRI Knowledge Hub’s formula

1.2. Deliverable Scope & Purpose

Scope: CCRI Knowledge hub connects cities and regions with a pool of experts who provide mentorship services tailored to different stages of the CE transition and specific user demands. This mentorship can include strategic advice, technical support, and guidance on policy and regulatory frameworks. Each mentee will have 12 online sessions of 2 hours with their mentors, ensuring consistent and thorough support. By leveraging the expertise of these mentors, cities and regions can navigate challenges more effectively and accelerate their progress towards a CE.

Purpose: The aim of this deliverable is to provide a user-friendly, operative, practical ad hoc guide to **experts** selected as **mentors** in charge of providing mentoring services in the framework of the CCRI Knowledge hub project. It contains practical information, tips and templates, the purpose of the mentoring activity, roles, rules of the programme as well as contractual and administrative issues.

1.3. Document's Audience

The **main audience of the document** are the external and internal experts selected to be mentors in the framework of CCRI Knowledge hub project.

1.4. List of abbreviations

CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CE	Circular Economy
CEA	Cost-Effectiveness Analysis
CCRI Knowledge Hub	CCRI Knowledge hub to leverage existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of Circular economy in Cities and Regions In Europe
KVC	Kveloce (CCRI Knowledge hub project coordinator)
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
ROI	Return on Investment
S-ROI	Social Return of Investment
SEIA	Socio-Economic Impact Assessment
SRL	Social-Readiness Level
UVEG	University of Valencia

2. Mentoring relationship

Figure 2: Mentoring relationship

The CCRI Knowledge hub mentoring programme is defined as one-to-one matching mentees with mentors based on their needs, goals, technical field and area of expertise. Internal (from the CCRI Knowledge hub consortium) and external mentors will provide personalised mentorship to regions and cities willing to advance the implementation of systemic CE solutions. A total of 38 mentees will receive the support of 36 in-house mentors (from the CCRI Knowledge hub consortium) and 40 external experts. Each mentee will have 12 online sessions of 2 hours with the mentor, and each mentor will develop 6 online session of 2 hours with their mentee. As far as possible, all sessions will be held online using Teams, but if needed mentors can use other tools they agree with the mentees in the first online session. As a result of the mentoring, CCRI Knowledge hub mentors will develop 38 individual / personalised Mentoring Plans.

2.1. Mentors

Experts within and outside¹ the consortium will provide the CCRI Knowledge hub mentoring programme. Both had been selected according to their experience in the four domains of the CCRI Knowledge hub project: (i) public engagement, (ii) innovation and technology, (iii) business models and financial support and (iv) impact evaluation.

2.1.1. Roles and responsibilities

Mentors' roles: In-house and external experts will provide tailored mentoring sessions to cities and regions according to their needs in the four main pillars of the CCRI Knowledge hub project. Although they can be also contacted to respond to specific needs arisen during the project execution according to their profile.

Mentors' responsibilities are:

- To organise 6 online sessions of 2 hours with their mentees. The logistics for the first online meeting will be provided by the CCRI Knowledge hub project coordinator (KVC) using Teams from Microsoft Office. The rest of the sessions will be organised by the mentor according to the timeline and platform agreed with the mentee during the first session.

¹ External experts were selected from an open call published in the CCRI website.

- To prepare in advance the 6 online sessions according to the needs of the city/region and the defined CCRI Knowledge hub Support Pathway shared by the CCRI Knowledge hub consortium.
- To draft an Individual/personalised Mentoring Plan identifying the mentee's expectations from their participation in the program, developing the mentee's objectives/goals and determining the pathways for realising these objectives and goals. For this Plan, mentors should use the template included as **Annex I** to this guide. This plan should be delivered after the first session with the mentee and shared with KVC (ccriknowledgehub@kveloce.com) and the CCRI Knowledge Hub partner responsible of the assigned mentee.
- To send the agenda for the second meeting and following meetings according to the objectives agreed on at the first meeting, at least 3 days prior to the corresponding meeting. In all the communications, please add KVC in copy (ccriknowledgehub@kveloce.com) and the CCRI Knowledge Hub partner responsible of the assigned mentee.
- For any presentation, use the ppt template provided by the CCRI Knowledge hub consortium.
- To ask questions to understand the needs / challenges of the mentee and foster his/her learning process.
- To provide constructive feedback.
- To encourage the mentee to ask questions, propose actions, identify barriers or challenges, etc.
- To monitor mentees' progress during the mentoring programme.
- At the end of the service, mentors should send the final version of the Individual/personalised Mentoring Plan to the mentees including in copy to KVC (as project coordinator) and UVEG (as responsible of the work package where this programme is planned) following the template included as **Annex I**.

2.1.2. Reward

In-house mentors will not receive extra compensation for the mentoring programme provided. They can justify their time spent as part of the project implementation.

For external experts, the mentor is charging a total of 900€ for conducting 6 sessions, including preparation time.

Figure 3: CCRI Knowledge Hub mentoring programme cost structure

2.2. Mentees

The mentorship provided by CCRI Knowledge hub experts offers valuable insights and guidance, helping cities and regions to overcome obstacles and leverage opportunities in their CE journey. Mentees will be selected via an open call for Expression of Interest that excludes CCRI pilots and fellows, trying to have a geographical representation of cities and regions with different characteristics (i.e. rural/urban).

2.2.1. Roles and responsibilities

Mentees' responsibilities are:

- To participate actively in the 12 online sessions of 2 hours each with the assigned mentors.
- To commit to dedicate these 24 hours with their mentors and the extra time required to prepare the meetings and discuss internally the issues arising from the mentoring programme.
- To ask questions and share experiences, information, etc. that reinforce the learning process.
- To identify actions, barriers, etc. for the feedback or suggestions received by the mentor.

2.2.2. Reward

Each mentee will receive 12 online sessions of 2 hours with their two mentors, that is a total of 24 hours of tailored mentoring programme. The assignment of experts will be based on their needs and context and the mentors' expertise and availability.

For each mentee, CCRI Knowledge hub mentors will draft an Individual/personalised Mentoring Plan identifying the mentee's expectations from their participation in the program, developing the mentee's objectives/goals and determining the pathways for realising these objectives and goals.

2.3. Shared responsibilities between mentors and mentees

In addition to the above responsibilities, both (mentors and mentees) should:

- Identify and agree together on the exact goals of the mentoring in relation to the city/region in question.
- Be fully committed to the mentoring programme, dedicating the time required for the online sessions and the extra time to prepare those sessions.
- Perform active listening: both should listen with full attention to the other and remove distractions as much as possible.
- Adopt a growth mindset: to embrace the learning opportunities that the mentoring programme offers.
- Be honest and transparent with the information shared to receive valuable support and guidance in the way to a CE.

- Read the proposed CCRI Knowledge hub Support Pathway before the first meeting.
- Keep confidentiality of the information exchange during the mentoring sessions
- Identify at least one takeaway at the end of each mentoring session.
- To complete the satisfaction survey at the end of the mentoring service received/provided (Annex III).

2.4. Language

Mentors and mentees can agree on the language to be used during the mentoring programme. In fact, in the selection process, a criterion to provide mentors with the same national language of the mentees has been included. Notwithstanding, Individual/personalised Mentoring Plans should be delivered in English as well as all the communication with the CCRI Knowledge hub partners. If there is no agreement on the language to use between the mentor and the mentee, the mentoring programme will be delivered in English.

3. Mentoring approach

3.1. General approach

From September 2024 to December 2026, the CCRI Knowledge hub project will support a community of mentors providing mentoring services for the different stages and demands of European cities and regions receiving the CCRI Knowledge hub Support Pathway. The CCRI Knowledge hub mentoring programme will be focused on the four CCRI Knowledge hub domains: (i) public engagement, (ii) innovation and technology, (iii) business models and financial support and (iv) impact evaluation; although mentors can be also contacted to respond specific needs arisen during the project execution according to their profile.

3.2. Dimension 1: Public engagement

For the regional and local adoption of CE, it is essential to address the Quadruple Helix of Stakeholders model², that brings together public administration, private industry (including financial and investing sectors), research, and civil society (Figure 4), considering the 5 levels of the Spectrum of Public Participation³:

1. Inform: to provide the public information to increase their understanding of the problem addressed, and the potential alternatives, opportunities and solutions.
2. Consult: to obtain feedback on analysis, alternatives, or decisions.
3. Involve: to work together with the public to ensure that their concerns and aspirations are understood and considered.
4. Collaborate: to collaborate with the public in the decision taking, considering alternatives and identifying the preferred solution.
5. Empower: to place the final decision according to the choice of the public.

Figure 4: Quadruple Helix of Stakeholders model

MENTORING PROGRAMME: according to the needs of the city or region, the mentor will support in the identification / mapping of stakeholders, propose participatory activities for their participation considering the different levels described above, etc. As described in the call for

² Salvioni, D.M., et al., 2020. Circular Economy and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy. Symphonya. Emerging Issues in Management, 1:26.

³ Chappell, B., 2016. Community engagement handbook: A model framework for leading practice in local government in South Australia

experts, the following table (Table 1) suggests some of the activities expected under this domain:

Table 1: Example of the mentoring activities to be implemented under the public engagement domain

	Examples of activities
Public engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting stakeholders mapping exercise (considering the quadruple helix) • Supporting and defining a stakeholder engagement plan • Supporting, defining and implementing activities under the 5 levels of public participation according to the cities' and regions' needs

Case studies of Public Engagement in CE:

In the **Involve phase** of A2C⁴ project funded by the H2020 (GA No 101036838), a practical activity is the Video Game Contest for Students, organised by one of the regional partners, aimed at engaging students through workshops focused on CE and programming. This initiative is part of the eco-school award programme and involves the City Halls of Murcia and Alhama (Spain). The first edition was launched in September 2022, with plans for expansion during the 2023-2024 school year.

Additionally, waste collection initiatives in local markets represent another public engagement effort. Several regional partners have collaborated with two market vendor associations to collect leftover waste from vending stalls, using containers provided by PRIMAFRIO. This community-based scheme highlights the importance of accessible educational materials in Spanish to ensure broad participation.

In the **Collaborate level**, stakeholder panels are a key activity. These panels, composed of partners, representatives from organisations, industries, and relevant associations, contribute to the development and implementation of systemic circular solutions. The panels provide recommendations for the project's outcomes and support the creation of new market routes for CE practices in various sectors. To gather detailed feedback, online meetings, pop-up events, and workshops were organised with stakeholders from A2C's targeted sectors.

3.3. Dimension 2: Innovation and technology

No single technology can act alone for a fully transition towards CE, but there are “enabling technologies”⁵ that have been recognised as facilitators of the circular transition, with many of them transversally applicable across industrial sectors. Enabling technologies are promoted at regional levels through the regions' Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3), which aim at enabling regional comparative advantages supported by local technological specialisation to stimulate regions to position themselves in a specific market or niche. However, the

⁴ <https://agro2circular.eu/>

⁵ KETs (Key Enabling Technologies Recently re-named Advanced Technologies for Industry, ATI) together with new emerging technologies

application of either cross-sectorial or sectorial (sector specific) enabling technologies still require knowledge on how to effectively link their application to be used as drivers of the CE.

MENTORING PROGRAMME: according to the needs and context of the city or region, the mentor will propose potential technologies to advance circularity, productivity, efficiency, customer satisfaction, and assess their potential impact in terms of progress in circularity, internationalisation and competitiveness. Developing an implementation plan for CE enabling technologies in a region/city requires a comprehensive strategy that addresses both local needs and available technological opportunities.

Table 2: Example of the mentoring activities to be implemented under the innovation and technology domain

	Examples of activities
Innovation and technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of the relevance of selected enabling technologies for a specific circular systemic solution. • Support and guidance for the design of the Implementation Plan: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Guidance for the selection of Technologies: Evaluate and select the most relevant enabling technologies for the established objectives, as well as potential impact, costs and feasibility of implementation. ○ Guidance on scalability and implementation strategies. ○ Guidance to define strategies for integration into existing urban infrastructure, ensuring interoperability and scalability. ○ Guidance on the governance model to support the implementation plan.

Case studies of Innovation and technology for cities and regions:

The Smart Cities Intraplatform Working Group (GICI)⁶- Spain, has promoted the development of a **catalogue of solutions for smart cities** to showcase national capabilities in this sector.

The aim is to be able to offer technology users (in this case cities) the existing possibilities and good practices. A **portfolio of solutions is offered in the form of an on-line platform and catalogue**, where the capacities of the industrial and technological fabric of the territory analysed, in this case Spain, can be visualised and updated in an agile and simple way.

The following figure shows the platform and catalogue.

⁶ [About | GiCI](#)

The screenshot displays the GICI Solutions Portfolio website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for ABOUT GICI, SOLUTIONS PORTFOLIO, DOCUMENTS, NEWS, EVENTS, and MEMBERS. Below the navigation, there are filters for 'Area' (set to '- Any -') and 'Maturity level' (set to 'Under development'). An 'Apply' button is visible next to the maturity level filter.

Status	Organization	Solution	Maturity level	Area	Line/ App. domain	Date
🟢	Urban Resilience, S.L.	SUMOSU stations, para facilitar a las corporaciones públicas la planificación estratégica, para la transición energética y el VE	En desarrollo	Movilidad e Intermodalidad	Sistemas Inteligentes De Transporte - ITS En El Entorno Urbano	Ver
🟢	Arnaiz Urbánica SL	uTHINGS	En desarrollo	Horizontal	TICs	Ver
🟢	Arnaiz Urbánica SL	uLinks www.urbilinks.com	En pruebas en entorno real	Horizontal	TICs	Ver
🟢	EGODUCO	Egroduco	En pruebas en entorno real	Horizontal	TICs	Ver
🟢	Defcon8 enterprise SL	Water monitor	Probado y validado	Energía y Medio Ambiente	Recursos Energéticos	Ver
🟢	LINEA CIUDADANA	Línea Ciudadana	Probado y validado	Gobierno y Servicios Sociales	Administración	Ver
🟢	Vocallia technologies SL	Asistente Virtual	En	Horizontal	TICs	Ver

To the right of the table is a promotional graphic for the 'FEB 2018 CATALOGO DE SOLUCIONES'. The graphic features a stylized, colorful image of a city's infrastructure, including roads and buildings, with the GICI logo in the top right corner.

3.4. Dimension 3: Business models and financial support

To ensure the long-term success of a CE initiative in any city or region, it is essential to perform a thorough economic analysis assessing its viability during the implementation phase. This study should extend beyond financial considerations, ensuring that the business model is tailored to the unique characteristics and needs of the local context. This initial analysis forms the foundation for evaluating the project's feasibility and ultimate success.

Beyond financial viability, the business model must be aligned with the socio-economic and regulatory environment of the region. It should promote sustainability and scalability, ensuring that the project not only succeeds in the short term but also grows and thrives in the long term. This evaluation will help identify opportunities for optimisation in both operational and financial aspects, establishing a solid basis for strategic decision-making that enhances the project's success within the CE framework.

MENTORING PROGRAMME: Based on the specific needs and context of each city or region, the mentoring program offers tailored support, including:

- **Case Studies or best practices analyses:** Providing insights into successful European cases / projects to compare, adapt, and refine the project's strategy; and to identify transferable elements.
- **Financial Model Creation:** Developing a simple financial model to project short- and long-term costs, as well as Return on Investment (ROI) and Social Return on Investment (S-ROI) under various scenarios. Or training on how to calculate ROI and S-ROI.
- **Scalability Assessment:** Evaluating the project's scalability from both technical and economic perspectives, including infrastructure, workforce, and regulatory considerations.
- **Market Integration Guide:** Creating a guide for integrating companies or projects into the local market by identifying regulatory, cultural, and logistical barriers.

- **Operational Cost Savings:** Analysing operational costs and determining potential economic and environmental savings. Conducting cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) and cost-benefit analysis (CBA).
- **Risk Mapping:** Developing a risk map that includes key factors influencing project implementation and strategies for mitigation, particularly related to S-ROI.

As described in the call for experts, the following table (Table 3) suggest some of the activities expected under this domain:

Table 3: Example of the mentoring activities to be implemented under the business models and financial support domain

	Examples of activities
Business models and financial support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs and Context Analysis: Understanding why the solution/new approach is needed • Identifying key stakeholders involved in the solution • Reviewing relevant regulations and policies • Business Model Development • Offering training to local teams on cost-effectiveness and cost-benefit analysis • Facilitating workshops to share lessons learned from other EU projects and apply them to the local context • Giving an overview of the funding opportunities and supporting the use of diverse funding mechanisms to finance the project • Exploitation Strategy Definition: Assisting in defining ROI and S-ROI strategies • Advising on strategies to scale successful projects • Soft-Landing Guide: Providing guidance for integrating into the region's business network and support organisations • Providing support to prepare a report on the financial and resource savings generated and how these can be reinvested in future initiatives • Ensuring alignment with sustainable finance and taxonomy frameworks • Risk Workshop: Collaborating with stakeholders to identify financial, economic, and social risks, and categorising them for project management purposes.

Case studies of Business models and financial support in CE:

Under the **AEDIB|NET project**, funded by H2020 (101017105)⁷, a Partnership Programme has been implemented with the objective of training European and African startups on how to establish, grow, and sustain a business. Additionally, it aims to facilitate connections and foster linkages between the two continents. As part of this initiative, a series of online training sessions have been conducted, covering topics such as the business model canvas and soft-

⁷ [AEDIB|NET - African European Digital Innovation Bridge Network \(aedibnet.eu\)](https://aedibnet.eu)

landing opportunities, involving key regional stakeholders including universities and governments. In recognition of the participants' significant engagement, they were invited to participate in one of two bootcamps, organised in conjunction with an event bringing together investors, regional and national authorities, universities, research centres, and business support organisations. The purpose of the event was to facilitate access to finance and promote the internationalisation of businesses to other countries or continents.

The EU-funded **CIRC4Life** project has developed new CE business models and has demonstrated them in the electrical and electronic equipment and agrifood sectors. Included in the project's deliverables, a report⁸ draws on evidence collected through in-depth interviews with companies involved in the project, as well as from additional cases of firms putting such models into practice to identify key barriers and enablers for the implementation of CE business models in the above two sectors. Collected data also provide insights on how the Covid-19 crisis has impacted the companies' circularity activities and overall business strategy. The report concludes with several identified policy gaps and recommendations for addressing them.

The **Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ)** GmbH, commonly known as GIZ, is a German federal enterprise that specialises in international development cooperation and education. GIZ has worked with multiple stakeholders to develop financing solutions that support CE projects, helping cities and businesses transition to more sustainable models. Their program⁹ offers insights and practical advice for financing CE initiatives. It includes case studies, best practices, and guidance on accessing financial support.

3.5. Dimension 4: Impact evaluation

MENTORING PROGRAMME: according to the needs and context of the city or region, the mentor will support the mentee to choose the suitable means to evaluate and monitor CE readiness and status of the city/region in question. This may include selection of the valid indicators based on existing indicator collections, such as ISO 59020 or the OECD Inventory of CE indicators and support the impact assessment of their selected individual activities/projects/initiatives. The focus is not on teaching individual assessment methods, such as e.g. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) or social readiness levels (SRL) but rather in supporting a better understanding of what these tools can be used for and under what circumstances. All this with the main aim to capacitate mentees to interpret information and be able to draw conclusions from those evaluations. As described in the call for experts, the following table (Table 4) suggest some of the activities expected under this domain:

Table 4: Example of the mentoring activities to be implemented under the impact evaluation domain

	Examples of activities
Impact evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploring CE readiness of the city/region

⁸ [rr2021-01_barriers-and-enablers-for-implementing-circular-economy-business-models.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

⁹ [Financing Circular Economy – Insights for Practitioners \(giz.de\)](#)

- Which factors, characteristics, strengths are there, and which are missing?
- What are the main development needs?
- Explore the different ways to assess impact
- In case needed, support improved understanding of selected methods, such as
 - Carrying out a lifecycle assessment (LCA)
 - Carrying out a socio-economic impact assessment (SEIA)
 - Exploring the social-readiness level (SRL)
- Peers benchmark assessment
- Impact communication

Case studies of Impact Evaluation in CE:

In the **CIRCULAR IMPACTS project**¹⁰ some case studies were conducted to understand good practices in the members states among different sectors and analyse the economic, societal and resource-efficiency impacts of different CE processes in comparison to the processes they are replacing. Among them:

Phosphorus Recycling from Manure¹¹ (Netherlands): an extensive LCA based on the International Standard Organisation (ISO) for LCA (ISO standards 14040, 14044 and 14071) was implemented with biochar production and with soil improver production compared to three state-of-the-art manure management processes. The LCA scope includes the environmental impacts of storage, transport and processing of manure and the application of nutrient rich products on agricultural land, including the avoidance of production of synthetic fertilizers. The LCA evaluation is based on several intermediate indicators and three endpoint indicators: human health, biodiversity and exhaustion of related resources. In relation to the economic analysis, the consortium analysed net costs per ton of manure, that resulted in 5-10 euros per ton lower than long distance transport, manure drying and manure separation, and the difference is larger when pig manure has a larger fraction of dry matter. Under the analysed conditions the circular process is profitable: the alternative disposal cost is more than about 15€ per ton pig manure, while the current disposal cost in the Netherlands is about 25€ per ton pig manure. About the social impacts, the employment is not expected to significant change because the circular technique is not labour intensive.

Car sharing¹² (Germany): deep desk research on existing reports and data of car sharing was performed combined with the extraction of data from Germany on Co2 emissions from motorised passenger vehicles, type of vehicles used in car-sharing, etc.

¹⁰ <https://www.ecologic.eu/14073>

¹¹ https://www.ecologic.eu/sites/default/files/project/2021/D4.5_Case-Study-Nutrient-Recycling_FINAL.pdf

¹² https://www.ecologic.eu/sites/default/files/publication/2019/2809-case-study-carsharing_final.pdf

4. Mentoring programme

4.1. Mentor's selection

The mentoring programme is defined as one-to-one matching mentees with mentors based on their needs, goals, technical field and area of expertise. In this sense, once the CCRI Knowledge hub Support Pathway is defined for a city or region, the external and/or internal mentors will be selected connecting their expertise with the needs of the city or region.

KVC will contact the internal and external mentors selected to confirm their availability to provide the mentoring programme in the proposed timeline. In the case of the external mentors, KVC will share with them the model of contract (**Annex II**) to be signed before starting the programme.

4.2. Documentation

Once confirmed the availability of the mentors, the documentation put at the disposal of the mentors is the following:

- ✓ this mentoring guide,
- ✓ the templates to be used by the mentor in the mentoring process (ppt for potential presentations during the online sessions, word document to be completed with the individual/personalised Mentoring Plan), and
- ✓ the draft of the CCRI Knowledge hub support pathway designed for the region or city to be mentored.

In addition, UVEG can share with mentors some user-friendly resources (materials and tools) related on the topics of the mentoring, together with the recording of some capacity building activities already performed by the CCRI Knowledge hub partners.

4.3. First contact

KVC will put in contact the mentors with the mentee by email reminding the main features of the mentoring programme:

- Timeline
- Support materials
- Commitment
- Results
- Platform to be used: preferably teams.

In this email, KVC will invite mentor and mentees to look for a suitable date and time to have the first online session. In this first session, the mentor and the mentee should agree on the following sessions. The calendar will be shared with KVC, but the mentor will be responsible to establish the different sessions using the platform agreed by the mentor and mentee. KVC,

UVEG and/or the CCRI Knowledge Hub partner in charge of the mentor will be invited to all the session and can attend any of them to check how the mentoring is being implemented.

According to the mentee needs, the assignment of the two mentors can be done in parallel or one after other.

4.4. Calendar and sessions

A total of 6 online sessions of 2 hours should be delivered to the mentee along 3 months. We recommend meeting on a bi-weekly basis during these three months (Figure 5).

Figure 5: CCRI Knowledge Hub mentoring timeline

Mentors are requested to read in advance the CCRI Knowledge hub Support Pathway of the mentee and the shared documentation to provide valuable mentoring services to the city or region. **During the first session**, the mentor should focus on understanding in-depth the needs/barriers of the mentee, define his/her goals/expectations of the mentoring service, and to determine the next steps. Some useful tools during this session can be: Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal factors (PESTEL) analysis; Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis; and Driving forces-Pressures-State-Impact-Response model (DPSIR). After the first session, it is important that each session has their own agenda in advance, at least with the points to be discussed so mentors and mentees can prepare the session.

The **final session** should be focused on monitoring the progress and the next steps agreed in previous meetings, exchanging feedback on the monitoring services, sharing takeaways,

sharing the final version of the Individual/personalised Mentoring Plan and evaluating the achievement of the objectives established in the first session.

The **middle sessions** (from the second to the fifth session) can be adapted according to the mentees needs and mentors' expertise according to the goals and expectations agreed in the first meeting. At the end of these meetings, it is recommended to share the takeaways for the mentor and mentee and determine the action plan (objectives, timeline, actions, resources and indicators) and next steps for the next meeting. During these meetings, different tools and methods can be used as the Funnel technique¹³ and the ReSOLVE framework¹⁴.

4.5. Report: Individual/personalised mentoring plan

The mentor should draft an Individual/personalised Mentoring Plan for the mentee identifying his/her expectations from his/her participation in the programme, developing the mentee's objectives/goals and determining the pathways for realising these objectives and goals. After the first meeting, a draft should be shared with the mentee and KVC. At the end of the mentoring programme, the Individual/personalised Mentoring Plan will be delivered to the mentee and the CCRI Knowledge hub consortium using the template included in the Annex I.

¹³ The funnel technique involves starting with general questions, and then drilling down, asking for more detail each time

¹⁴ <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/growth-within-a-circular-economy-vision-for-a-competitive-europe>

5. Conclusions

CCRI Knowledge hub connects cities and regions with a pool of experts who provide mentorship services tailored to different stages of the CE transition and specific user demands. This mentorship can include strategic advice, technical support, and guidance on policy and regulatory frameworks framed in an **Individual/personalised mentoring plan**. The CCRI Knowledge hub mentoring programme is defined as one-to-one matching mentees with mentors based on their needs, goals, technical field and area of expertise. For that, the individual plan consists on a total of 12 online sessions of 2 hours between the mentor and the mentee, ensuring consistent and thorough support. A total of **38 mentees** will receive the support of **36 in-house mentors** (from the CCRI Knowledge hub consortium) and **40 external experts** from September 2024 to December 2026. Both had been selected according to their experience in the four domains of the CCRI Knowledge hub project: (i) public engagement, (ii) innovation and technology, (iii) business models and financial support and (iv) impact evaluation although mentors can be also contacted to respond specific needs arisen during the project execution according to their profile. By leveraging the expertise of these mentors, cities and regions can navigate challenges more effectively and accelerate their progress towards a CE.

In this context, this deliverable provides a user-friendly, operative, practical ad hoc guide to the experts selected as mentors in charge of providing mentoring services in the framework of the CCRI Knowledge hub project. It contains practical information, tips and templates, the purpose of the mentoring activity, roles, rules of the programme as well as contractual and administrative issues that guided experts through the Mentoring process (Figure 6):

Figure 6: CCRI Knowledge Hub mentoring process

The one-to-one mentoring programme should be delivered in 3 months, and for this it is suggested bi-weekly meetings between the mentor and the mentee.

The **results** of the CCRI Knowledge hub programme are the following:

- 38 individual / personalised Mentoring Plans
- 38 mentees received support for implementing CE solutions
- 76 mentors engaged (36 in-house plus 40 external)
- 456 mentoring sessions

6. Annexes

ANNEX I: Template for the individual/personalised mentoring plan

Name of the mentor		
City/region receiving the mentoring		
Name of the mentee		
Dimension addressed	<input type="checkbox"/> Public engagement <input type="checkbox"/> Innovation and technology <input type="checkbox"/> Business models, market assessment, and financial support <input type="checkbox"/> Impact evaluation <input type="checkbox"/> Other (on demand):	
& Online sessions	DATE	TIME
1 st online session		
2 nd online session		
3 rd online session		
4 th online session		
5 th online session		
Final online session		
Mentee`s expectations	•	
Objectives of the mentoring programme	•	
Pathways for realising these objectives		
Outcomes of the mentoring programme		
Other inputs:		

ANNEX II: Template for the mentors' contracts

CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB

Knowledge hub to leverage existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of Circular economy in Cities and Regions In Europe

CONTRACT AGREEMENT IN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB PROJECT

NAME OF CONTRACT (HE Grant Agreement n. 101135174)

The objective of the contract in the framework of the CCRI knowledge hub project is to provide a comprehensive mentoring program facilitated by experts outside the consortium.

Contract number: CCRI knowledge hub Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.

This contract (hereinafter referred to as "the Contract") is made and entered into on [Date], by and between:

1. Senior Europa, S.L., Plaza la Reina 19, 46003 València, Spain (hereafter "the contracting party"), represented by Maite Ferrando, representing the Consortium of the "Knowledge hub to leverage existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of Circular economy in Cities and Regions In Europe" funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement 101135174.
2. [Name of the Expert], an individual with principal address at [Expert's Address] (hereinafter referred to as "the Expert").

The parties referred to above have agreed to enter into this Contract under the terms and conditions below. By signing this Contract, the Expert confirms that s/he has read, understood and accepted the Contract and all its obligations and conditions:

6.1.1. TERMS AND CONDITIONS

6.1.1.1. CHAPTER 1: GENERAL

ARTICLE 1 — OBJECT OF THE CONTRACT

The object of this Contract is the provision of expert services by the Expert to the Contracting Party in relation to the CCRI Knowledge hub project under the European Union Grant Agreement 101135174.

Funded by
the European Union

Concretely, the objective of the contract in the framework of the CCRI Knowledge hub project is to provide a comprehensive mentoring program facilitated by experts outside the consortium. These experts have been selected based on their experience in four key domains of the CCRI Knowledge hub project: (i) Public engagement, (ii) innovation and technology, (iii) business models and financial support, and (iv) impact evaluation. The mentors will deliver tailored mentoring sessions to cities and regions, addressing their specific needs in these four main pillars. Additionally, the mentors can be approached to address any specific issues that arise during the project execution, leveraging their specialised profiles.

6.1.1.2. CHAPTER 2: WORK TO BE PROVIDED

ARTICLE 2 — TASKS TO BE ACCOMPLISHED

The Expert agrees to perform the tasks outlined in Annex 2 - Terms of Reference, which includes specific duties, timelines, and deliverables.

ARTICLE 3 — WORKING ARRANGEMENTS

The Expert's work will start on DD/MM/YYYY and will terminate on DD/MM/YYYY.

The Expert will work remotely adhering to the timelines and quality standards outlined in Annex 2.

The Expert will spend the amount working hours pre-approved and requested to carry out the tasks. The number of working hours are included in Annex 2 and in Deliverable D.3.4. Mentoring Guide.

The Expert will use his/her own working space and equipment and the contracting party will not make available any.

6.1.1.3. CHAPTER 3: FEES, ALLOWANCES AND EXPENSES

ARTICLE 4 — FEE

Following the EC policy for reimbursement of external experts, experts will be reimbursed at a rate of €75 per hour for up to 12 working hours, including preparation time (all taxes included), for the completion of their tasks in accordance with Annex 2.

ARTICLE 5 — TRAVEL EXPENSES

No travel expenses will be reimbursed under this contract. All activities and tasks are expected to be completed without incurring any travel-related costs.

6.1.1.4. CHAPTER 4: RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS OF THE PARTIES

ARTICLE 6 — PERFORMANCE OF THE CONTRACT

The Expert shall perform the tasks with due diligence, efficiency, and in accordance with the highest professional standards.

The Expert has been identified based on her/his previous experience in four key domains of the CCRI Knowledge hub project and through an open call together with the CCRI: (i) Public engagement, (ii) innovation and technology, (iii) business models and financial support, and (iv) impact evaluation.

The Expert must perform the Contract in compliance with its provisions and all legal obligations under applicable EU, international and national law. The Expert must do so fully, within the set deadlines and to the highest professional standards. The Expert must, in particular, ensure compliance with the Code of Conduct (see Annex 1).

The terms and conditions of this Contract do not constitute an employment agreement with the contracting party.

If the Expert cannot fulfil his/her obligations, s/he must immediately inform the contracting party.

ARTICLE 7 — REPORTING

The Expert is required to submit to the project coordinator PhD. Mireia Ferri a first version and final version of the Mentoring plan as specified in Annex 2, detailing the work accomplished and results achieved. A template for this plan is included in the D3.4 Mentoring guide. If requested, the Expert should send to PhD Mireia Ferri or designated person the supporting documentation (original supporting documents i.e. Mentoring Plan for each mentee¹⁵) as evidence that the Contract is performed correctly. The Expert must keep copies of all records and supporting documentation for three years starting from the date of the last payment. If there are on-going checks, audits, investigations, appeals, litigation or pursuit of claims, the Expert must keep the records and supporting documents until these procedures end.

ARTICLE 8 — REQUEST FOR PAYMENTS

The Expert shall be paid for the days worked as specified in Article 4 and Article 5, respectively, according to the schedule outlined in Annex 2.

The contracting party shall not be responsible for withholding taxes with respect to the Expert's compensation under regulations other than those of the contracting Spanish company. Furthermore, the contracting party does not take responsibility for any misconduct or errors made by the Expert concerning the taxation system effective in the Expert's fiscal residence.

The Expert shall invoice upon submission of the final mentoring plan (the final report) and/or according to the following schedule:

By the end of January 2025

By the end of January 2026

By the end of November 2026

Claims and/or invoices should be accompanied by the respective activity or period report and are limited to 6 working days throughout the entire project.

¹⁵ Please see deliverable *D.3.4. Mentoring Guide*

ARTICLE 9 — PAYMENT

Payment will be made within 30 days after the submission of the expense's settlement document of each activity report or travel.

Payments are further subject to the contracting party's acceptance of report(s), including time records, and of the invoice.

Payments will be made in euros.

Payments will be made to the bank account specified by the Expert in the invoice.

ARTICLE 10 — OWNERSHIP AND USE OF THE RESULTS (INCLUDING INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS)

The contracting party must fully and irrevocably acquire the ownership of all the results under this Contract including any rights in any of the results listed in this Contract, or others that might be agreed upon during the contractual period, including copyright and other intellectual or industrial property rights.

ARTICLE 11 — PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

1. Processing of Personal Data by the Contracting Company:

The Contracting Company undertakes to process all personal data provided by the Expert in compliance with the current Spanish data protection regulations, as well as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) and Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, on the Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights. The Expert hereby consents to the processing of their personal data for the purpose of fulfilling the obligations under this contract, which may include the sharing of data for invoicing and legally mandated provisions. Such data will be used solely for the purposes established in this contract and will be processed by the data controller designated by the Contracting Company. The Expert shall have the right to access, rectify, and, where applicable, erase the provided data, as well as to exercise any other rights recognized by the applicable legislation on data protection. The data will be retained for the duration of the contract and for the periods legally established.

2. Processing of Personal Data by the Expert, Data Processor:

The Expert, acting as a data processor, undertakes to process only the personal data provided by the Contracting Company in accordance with the instructions set forth in this contract and in compliance with Spanish and European data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, on the Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights.

The Expert shall implement the following technical and organizational measures to ensure the rights of data subjects:

- a. **Transparency and Access to Information:** The Expert commits to providing data subjects with clear and comprehensive information regarding the processing of their personal data,

- including the purposes of the processing, the categories of personal data processed, the recipients of the data, and the rights of data subjects under data protection regulations.
- b. **Right of Access and Rectification:** The Expert will facilitate the exercise of the right of access and rectification of personal data by data subjects, responding promptly to requests for access and rectification of data.
 - c. **Confidentiality and Data Security:** The Expert will implement appropriate security measures to protect personal data against unauthorized access, disclosure, alteration, or accidental or unlawful destruction, including data encryption, access control, and anonymization of data where possible.
 - d. **Limitation of Processing:** The Expert will process personal data only in accordance with the documented instructions of the Contracting Company, refraining from using the data for purposes other than those authorized.
 - e. **Notification of Data Breaches:** In the event of a data breach that may affect the rights and freedoms of data subjects, the Expert will notify the Contracting Company without undue delay, providing detailed information about the nature of the breach and the measures taken to mitigate its effects.

The Expert agrees to comply with these measures and to cooperate fully with the Contracting Company to ensure compliance with data protection regulations and protect the rights of data subjects.

ARTICLE 12 — CHECKS, AUDITS AND INVESTIGATIONS

The contracting party may — during the implementation of the action or afterwards — carry out checks and audits to ascertain compliance with the proper implementation of the tasks (including assessment reports) under this Contract and whether the Expert is meeting his/her obligations. It may do so throughout the Contract's validity and up to two years after the last payment is made. The Expert must provide — within the deadline requested — any information and data in addition to reports and cost claims already submitted.

6.1.1.5. CHAPTER 5: EFFECTS OF BREACHING CONTRACTUAL OBLIGATIONS

ARTICLE 13 — SUSPENSION OF THE PAYMENT DEADLINE

The contracting party may at any point suspend the payment deadline (see Article 9), if an invoice cannot be processed because it does not comply with the Contract's provisions.

The contracting party must formally notify the Expert of the suspension and the reasons for it.

If the payment deadline has been suspended due to the non-compliance of the reports (see Article 3) and the revised report or deliverables or payment request is not submitted or was submitted but is also rejected, the contracting party may also terminate the Contract (see Article 18).

ARTICLE 14 — REDUCTION OR REJECTION OF FEES

The contracting party may reject (parts of) the fees if they do not fulfil the conditions set out in Article 4. The contracting party may reduce the fee if the Expert is in breach of any of their other obligations under the Contract (including the obligations set out in the Code of Conduct).

The contracting party must formally notify the Expert of its intention, include the reasons why, and invite him/her to submit any observations within 30 days of receiving notification. If the contracting party does not accept these observations, it will formally notify confirmation of the rejection or reduction.

ARTICLE 15 — REJECTION OF CLAIMS FOR ALLOWANCES

The contracting party may reject claims for allowances if they do not fulfil the conditions set out in Article 5. The contracting party must formally notify the Expert of its intention, include the reasons why and invite him/her to submit any observations within 30 days of receiving notification. If the contracting party does not accept these observations, it will formally notify confirmation of the rejection.

ARTICLE 16 — RECOVERY OF UNDUE AMOUNTS

The contracting party may recover any amount that was paid but was not due under the Contract.

The contracting party must formally notify the Expert of its intention, include the reasons why and invite him/her to submit any observations within 30 days of receiving notification. If the contracting party does not accept these observations, it will confirm recovery by formally notifying a ‘debit note’ that specifies the payment terms and date. The Expert must repay the amount specified in the debit note to the contracting party.

ARTICLE 17 — SUSPENSION OF THE CONTRACT

The contracting party may suspend implementation of the Contract or any part of it, if the Expert is not able to fulfil his/her obligation to carry out the work required (see Article 6).

The contracting party must formally notify the Expert of its intention, include the reasons why and invite him/her to submit any observations within seven days of receiving notification. If the contracting party does not accept these observations, it will formally notify confirmation of the suspension.

The suspension will take effect on the date the notification is sent by the contracting party.

If the reasons for suspending implementation of the Contract are no longer valid, the suspension may be lifted, and implementation may be resumed. The contracting party will formally notify the Expert if the suspension is lifted and the Contract will be amended, if necessary (see Article 22), unless it has been terminated (see Article 18). Expenses incurred while the contract is suspended are not eligible.

ARTICLE 18 — TERMINATION OF THE CONTRACT

The contracting party may at any moment terminate the Contract if the Expert: (a) is not performing their tasks or is performing them poorly; or (b) has committed substantial errors, irregularities or

fraud, or is in serious breach of their obligations under the selection procedure or under the Contract, including false declarations and obligations relating to the Code of Conduct.

The contracting party must formally notify the Expert of its intention, include the reasons why and invite him/her to submit any observations within 30 days of receiving notification. If the contracting party does not accept these observations, it will formally notify confirmation of the termination.

The termination will take effect on the date the notification is sent by the contracting party.

The Expert may at any moment terminate the Contract if s/he is not able to fulfil their obligations in carrying out the work required (see Article 6).

The Expert must formally notify the contracting party and include the reasons why by giving 15 days' notice.

The termination will take effect on the date the contracting party will formally notify confirmation of the termination.

Only fees for days actually worked before termination may be paid. The Expert must submit the payment request for the tasks already executed on the date of termination within 30 days from the date of termination or, if preferred, after some established periods (see article 8). On termination of the Contract, the contracting party may hire another Expert to carry out or finish the work. It may claim from the Expert all extra costs incurred while doing this, without prejudice to any other rights or guarantees it may have under the Contract.

ARTICLE 19 — LIABILITY FOR DAMAGES

The contracting party cannot be held liable for any damage caused or sustained by the Expert or a third party during or as a consequence of performing the Contract, except in the event of the contracting party's wilful misconduct or gross negligence.

ARTICLE 20 — FORCE MAJEURE

'Force majeure' means any situation or event that:

- prevents either party from fulfilling their obligations under the Contract; - was unforeseeable, exceptional and beyond the parties' control;
- was not due to error or negligence on their part; and
- proves to be inevitable in spite of exercising due diligence.

A force majeure must be immediately and formally notified to the contracting party. Notification must include details of the situation's nature, likely duration and expected effects.

The party faced with a force majeure will not be held in breach of its contractual obligations if the force majeure has prevented it from fulfilling them.

6.1.1.6. CHAPTER 6: FINAL PROVISIONS

ARTICLE 21 — COMMUNICATION BETWEEN THE PARTIES

Communication under the Contract (e.g. information, requests, submissions, formal notifications, etc.) must be made in writing (in electronic form), send by e-mail and bear the Contract's number.

Communications by e-mail are considered to have been made when they are sent by the sending party to one of the addressees listed below, unless the sending party receives a message of non-delivery.

For the contracting agency: administracion@kveloce.com and CCRIknowledgehub@kveloce.com

For the Expert: *[include email address]*

ARTICLE 22 — AMENDMENTS TO THE CONTRACT

In justified cases — and provided that the amendment does not entail changes to the Contract which would call into question the selection procedure — any party may request an amendment. Amendments must be made before new contractual obligations are enforced.

The party requesting an amendment must formally notify the other party together with the reasons why. The party receiving the request must formally notify its agreement or disagreement, within 30 days of receiving notification.

ARTICLE 23 — APPLICABLE LAW AND DISPUTE SETTLEMENT

This Contract is governed by Spanish law.

Disputes concerning the Contract's interpretation, application or validity that cannot be settled amicably must be brought before the court of Valencia.

ARTICLE 24 — ENTRY INTO FORCE

This Contract enters into force on the day on which the last party signs. Done in two copies in English.

This Contract and its Annexes constitute the entire agreement between the parties. Any amendments or modifications must be made in writing and signed by both parties.

SIGNATURES

[Place], [Data]

Expert name

Include expert name

For the contracting party:

Name of the representative of the contracting party

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6.1.1.7. ANNEX 1 – CODE OF CONDUCT FOR EXPERTS

ARTICLE 1 – PERFORMANCE OF THE CONTRACT

1. The Expert works independently, in a personal capacity and not on behalf of any organization.
2. The Expert must: (a) carry out his/her work in a confidential and fair way according to Annex 2 to the Contract (Terms of Reference) (b) assist the contracting party or relevant service to the best of their abilities, professional skills, knowledge and applying the highest ethical and moral standards (c) follow any instructions and time-schedules given by the contracting party or relevant service and deliver consistently high-quality work.
3. The Expert should not delegate another person to carry out the work or be replaced by any other person.

ARTICLE 2 – OBLIGATIONS OF IMPARTIALITY

1. The Expert must perform his/her work impartially. To this end, the Expert is required to inform the contracting party of any conflicts of interest arising in the course of his/her work.
2. Definition of the conflict of interest: a conflict of interest exists if an Expert: (a) has any vested personal direct economic interests in relation to the questions upon which s/he is asked to give advice (b) or his/her organisation, more than other organisations, stands to benefit directly or indirectly as a direct result of the work carried out (c) is in any other situation that compromises his/her ability to carry out the work impartially.

The contracting party will decide whether a conflict of interest exists, taking account of the objective circumstances, available information and related risks when an Expert is in any other situation that could cast doubt on their ability to carry out their work, or that could reasonably appear to do so in the eyes of an external third party.

3. Consequences of a situation of conflict of interest: (a) If a conflict of interest is reported by the Expert or established by the contracting party, the Expert must not carry out the work (b) If a conflict becomes apparent in the course of their work, the Expert must inform immediately the contracting party. If a conflict is confirmed, the Expert must stop carrying out their work. If necessary, the Expert will be replaced. If it is revealed in the course of their work that an Expert has knowingly concealed a conflict of interest, the Expert will be immediately excluded, and sanctions will apply (see Articles 14, 15, 16 and 18 of the Contract). Any work already carried out by the Expert will be declared null.

ARTICLE 3 - OBLIGATIONS OF CONFIDENTIALITY

1. The contracting party and the Expert must treat confidentially any information and documents, in any form (i.e. paper or electronic), disclosed in writing or orally in relation to the performance of the Contract.
2. The Expert undertakes to observe strict confidentiality in relation to their work. To this end, the Expert must not use or disclose, directly or indirectly confidential information or

documents for any purpose other than fulfilling their obligations under the Contract without prior written approval of the contracting party.

6.1.1.8. ANNEX 2 - TERMS OF REFERENCE

Name of the Expert: [please include the full name of the expert]

BACKGROUND

This Contract comes in the framework of the CCRI Knowledge hub project Grant Agreement n. 101135174, a Coordination & Support Action (CSA) to enhance collaboration between Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's (CCRI) supporting organisations.

THE CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB CSA

CCRI Knowledge hub aims to increase the impact of the existing Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) by enlarging the network of involved stakeholders, bringing together the knowledge and critical mass already developed around Circular Economy (CE) implementation and building upon the CE stakeholder platform. The goal is to promote and make the CE concept a reality in EU cities and regions, particularly those in the early stage of CE transition. To reach its objective, CCRI Knowledge hub acts as a “Knowledge hub”, leveraging existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of CE in EU cities and regions. CCRI Knowledge hub’s formula is based on three principles (Figure 1): (a) easy access to systematised workable knowledge; (b) tailored mentoring according to users’ needs and (c) effective awareness-raising to make the CE more desirable, that build upon four main dimensions: (i) Public engagement; (ii) Innovation and technology; (iii) Business models and financial support; and (iv) Impact evaluation. CCRI Knowledge hub gathers a multidisciplinary expert consortium of 11 partners from 6 EU countries (research and technological centres, universities, research organisations, international networks and associations, regional authorities as well as specialised companies and SMEs) that bring in complementary skills and competences to achieve the project’s objectives.

Figure 1: CCRI Knowledge Hub’s formula

CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB members will act as experts supporting the project execution and implementation phases. In this way, CCRI Knowledge hub will co-design research with the involvement of relevant and diverse stakeholders.

EXPECTED TASKS

- **Organize Online Sessions:** Mentors are required to organise 6 online sessions, each lasting 2 hours, with their mentees. The first session's logistics will be handled by the CCRI Knowledge hub project coordinator (KVC) using Microsoft Teams. The remaining sessions

will be organised by the mentor according to the timeline and platform agreed upon with the mentee during the first session.

- **Prepare for Sessions:** Mentors must prepare in advance for each of the 6 online sessions, tailoring the content to the specific needs of the city or region and following the CCRI Knowledge hub Support Pathway provided by the CCRI Knowledge hub consortium.
- **Draft a Personalized Mentoring Plan:** Mentors are to draft an Individual/Personalised Mentoring Plan that identifies the mentee's expectations, outlines objectives and goals, and determines pathways to achieve these objectives. The template to this end can be found in deliverable D.3.4. Mentoring Guide and should be sent to the CCRI Knowledge hub project coordinator (Mireia Ferri) & Support services responsible (Carlos Serra) after the first online session with the mentee.
- **Send Meeting Agendas:** Mentors must send the agenda for the second and subsequent meetings at least 3 days prior to each meeting. These agendas should align with the objectives agreed upon in the first meeting.
- **Use CCRI Knowledge hub Presentation Templates:** For any presentations during the mentoring sessions, mentors are required to use the PowerPoint template provided by the CCRI Knowledge hub consortium.
- **Engage and Understand Mentee Needs:** Mentors should ask questions to understand the mentee's needs and challenges, fostering a supportive learning environment.
- **Provide Constructive Feedback:** Mentors are expected to give constructive feedback to support the mentee's development and progress.
- **Encourage Mentee Participation:** Mentors should encourage mentees to ask questions, propose actions, and identify any barriers or challenges they face.
- **Monitor Mentee Progress:** Throughout the mentoring program, mentors are responsible for monitoring the progress of their mentees.
- **Submit Final Mentoring Plan:** At the end of the mentoring program, mentors must send the final version of the Individual/Personalised Mentoring Plan to the mentees, with copies to KVC (as project coordinator) and UVEG (responsible for the work package in which this program is planned).
 - Final Mentoring plan report: The final report must be submitted within one week after the completion of the final mentoring session.
 - Content:
 - A comprehensive overview of all mentoring activities conducted over the 3 months
 - An evaluation of the mentee's progress and the achievement of objectives set out in the initial session
 - Feedback from both the mentor and mentee on the mentoring process
 - Recommendations for future actions or areas for continued development

Submission: All reports should be submitted via email to both the CCRI Knowledge hub project coordinator (KVC) and UVEG (as responsible for the work package) in accordance with the timelines specified above.

SCHEDULE

Mentors should deliver 6 bi-weekly, 2-hour online sessions over 3 months, beginning with an initial session to assess the mentee's needs and goals, using tools like PESTEL and SWOT analysis, followed by customized middle sessions, and concluding with a final session to review progress, provide feedback, and finalize the Individual/Personalized Mentoring Plan.

ANNEX III: Mentoring satisfaction survey

Annex III.I: Satisfaction survey for mentors

Introduction:

Thank you for participating as a mentor in the CCRI Knowledge hub programme. Your feedback is essential for improving the mentoring process. Please rate your experience based on the following statements using a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "strongly disagree" and 5 means "strongly agree." Open-ended questions are included to gather additional insights.

Individual/personalized Mentoring Plan n°: _____

Section 1: Overall Satisfaction

1. The mentoring programme met my expectations as a mentor.
2. The mentoring sessions were well-structured, and I was able to provide relevant support.
3. I had clear objectives and guidelines for the mentoring programme.
4. The mentee(s) I worked with were engaged and actively participated in the sessions.
5. The Individual/Personalised Mentoring Plan helped me to guide the mentoring process effectively.

Open-ended question:

6. What aspect of the mentoring programme did you find most rewarding as a mentor?

Section 2: Content-Specific Feedback

7. I felt confident in my knowledge of the topics I covered (public engagement, innovation and technology, business models, or impact evaluation).
8. The resources and materials provided to support my mentoring activities were adequate and helpful.
9. I was able to provide tailored advice and solutions based on the specific needs of the mentee(s).
10. The mentoring programme helped the mentee(s) take clear steps towards their circular economy goals.

Open-ended question:

11. What additional resources or support would have been useful for you during the mentoring programme?

Section 3: Communication and Process

12. Communication between myself and the mentee(s) was clear and effective.
13. The scheduling and logistics of the mentoring sessions were smooth and easy to manage.
14. The mentee(s) were open to feedback and actively engaged in discussions.
15. I was provided with sufficient background information about the mentee(s)' goals and challenges.
16. The online tools and platforms used for the mentoring sessions (e.g., Teams) worked well.

Open-ended question:

17. How could the communication and process of the mentoring programme be improved?
Can a digital platform support the mentoring process and communication between you and your mentee? How?

Section 4: Impact and Follow-up

18. I would be interested in participating in future mentoring programmes with CCRI Knowledge hub.

19. I feel that the CCRI Knowledge hub mentoring programme is beneficial for promoting circular economy solutions in cities and regions.

20. I had enough support from the CCRI Knowledge hub team during the mentoring process.

21. I would recommend this mentoring programme to other experts who want to contribute to the circular economy transition.

Open-ended question:

22. What specific improvements or changes would you suggest for future mentoring programmes?

Any other inputs you want to share: _____

Annex III.II: Satisfaction survey for mentees

Introduction:

Thank you for participating in the CCRI Knowledge hub mentoring programme. Your feedback is very important to us and will help improve future mentoring services. Please rate your experience in the programme based on the following statements using a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "strongly disagree" and 5 means "strongly agree." There are also open-ended questions for additional input.

Individual/personalized Mentoring Plan n°: _____

Section 1: Overall Satisfaction

1. The mentoring programme met my expectations.
2. The mentoring sessions were well-organised and structured.
3. I am satisfied with the quality of the interaction with my mentor(s).
4. The mentoring sessions helped me define practical next steps for implementing circular economy practices
5. I found the personalised mentoring plan to be useful for guiding the sessions.

Open-ended question:

6. What aspect of the mentoring programme did you find the most valuable?

Section 2: Content-Specific Feedback

7. The mentor(s) had in-depth knowledge of the specific areas we focused on (public engagement, innovation and technology, business models, or impact evaluation).
8. The resources and materials provided by the mentor(s) (e.g., presentations, templates) were useful for me.
9. I feel more confident in applying the knowledge I gained during the mentoring sessions to my daily work.

[Here - Inclusion of a specific set of questions to assess the usefulness of the mentoring that will be tailored depending on 1) the dimension of the project on which the mentee is receiving support (public engagement, innovation and technology, business models, or impact evaluation); 2) the specific and individualised objectives set in the Mentoring Plan]

Open-ended question:

10. What topics or areas would you like to explore further in future mentoring sessions or workshops?

Section 3: Communication and Process

11. The communication between myself and my mentor(s) was clear and effective.
12. The scheduling and logistics of the mentoring sessions were smooth and convenient.
13. I was given enough time during each session to discuss my challenges and ideas.
14. The mentor(s) encouraged open dialogue and active participation during the sessions.
15. The format and tools (e.g., Teams platform) used for the online mentoring sessions were appropriate and worked well.

Open-ended question:

16. Is there anything you would suggest improving the mentoring process or communication between mentors and mentees? Can a digital platform support the mentoring process and communication between you and your mentor(s)? How?

Section 4: Impact and Follow-up

17. The mentoring programme helped me take significant steps towards achieving my goals.

18. I am clear on the next steps I need to take after the conclusion of the mentoring programme.

19. I feel supported by the CCRI Knowledge hub team to continue making progress in my circular economy initiatives.

20. I would recommend the CCRI Knowledge hub mentoring programme to other stakeholders, cities or regions.

Open-ended question:

21. What specific improvements would you suggest for the mentoring programme in the future?

Any other inputs you want to share: _____

